

D5.4 – Final report on Data Infrastructure update and extension

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Project co-ordinator name, Title and Organisation: Prof. Franco Niccolucci, PIN Scrl - Polo Universitario "Città di Prato"

Tel: +39 0574 602578

E-mail: franco.niccolucci@pin.unifi.it

Project website address: www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu

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Author: **Julian Richards**
University of York: Archaeology Data Service

Contributing partners: **Ceri Binding, University of South Wales**
Doug Tudhope, University of South Wales
Alessia Bardi, CNR-ISTI
Carlo Meghini, CNR-ISTI
Achille Felicetti, PIN

Quality control: **Sheena Bassett, PIN**
Paola Ronzino, PIN

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1. Executive Summary

The deliverable reports work undertaken in Work package 5 under Tasks 5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 5.4, 5.5 and 5.7 during the final 12 months of the project, providing an update to D5.3, and assessing what has been accomplished during the lifetime of the project. The final DMP produced within Task 5.6 is reported in D5.5. Related activity has been reported in D4.3 and D4.4.

ARIADNEplus has delivered a transformational upgrade and extension of the original research data infrastructure created within the preceding ARIADNE project (2013-17). It has extended ARIADNE in several dimensions:

1. Wider geographical coverage with new partners.
2. Wider disciplinary coverage with a greater emphasis on the sub-domains of palaeo-anthropology, bioarchaeology, environmental archaeology, dating methods, and on the archaeology of standing structures.
3. The time span covered.
4. The depth of database integration, with a greater degree of item-level integration.
5. Greater integration of texts.
6. Broader audiences.
7. Greater range of services.

This deliverable describes the final update procedures which are being followed by partners, and outlines the steps in the aggregation pipeline. This was initially presented in D5.2 but it is rehearsed here for the sake of completeness and including updates. There are two options for aggregation: the standard approach using a suite of tools for the semi-automated aggregation of large data-sets, and a basic approach for the manual upload of small numbers of records. The majority of partners have used the standard approach, but a small number used the FastCat tool for upload of a few records, and the tool has also proved invaluable for the addition of bespoke Collection records for harvested resources.

Partners following the standard approach must:

1. Describe their data according to the AO-Cat using the 3M tool, usually with one mapping per partner.
2. Map subject terms to the Getty AAT using the Vocabulary Matching Tool.
3. Define any period terms used so that they are uploaded to Period0.

Where temporal data needs cleaning to create consistent use of date ranges and periods, partners use an additional tool, Time Spans, to normalise date ranges. They must also ensure that spatial data is compliant with WGS 84.

Partners using FastCat instead manually enter their data records in a spreadsheet-like tool, where the column headings already correspond to AO-Cat core mandatory fields, so that there can be a single mapping covering multiple partners.

Data aggregated by both routes is then transformed into the ARIADNE triplestore, and is also used to create the indices used to power OpenSearch in the ARIADNE portal. Data is initially loaded into a “staging” portal for checking, before it is published in the “public” portal.¹

Aggregation proceeds according to an agreed priority list and is managed via regular meetings of the aggregation task force, which comprises representatives of UoY-ADS, PIN, CNR, USW and FORTH, with SND often in attendance to deal with any issues which require changes to the portal interface. Progress is also monitored by a software tool, Activity Dash (implemented by FORTH in WP14), which makes it easier to monitor the progress across a large number of partners, but use is also made of the ARIADNE D4Science and Redmine help desks, the shared Google document notes from the aggregation task force meetings, and also email.

Since the interim deliverable D5.3 at M36, we have aggregated an additional 1.5 million data resources covering the majority of ARIADNE subject types: archaeological sites and monuments, fieldwork events, fieldwork reports, fieldwork archives, inscriptions, dates, artefacts, rock art, building surveys, maritime, scientific analyses, burials and coins. The workflow both for new datasets and also that for adding updates to existing datasets is now tried and tested. At M48 we have over 182 million triples in the public knowledge base (387 million including the inferred triples), and over 3.3 million resources listed in the public portal. Our focus for the last months of the current project has been to complete the aggregation of datasets from the remaining data provider partners and associate partners, but also to make provision for sustainability of the infrastructure and to develop a sustainable business model for continued updates from existing partners, as well as for the addition of new datasets from organisations wanting to join (see D6.5).

Since M36 we have also continued the development of application profiles for data types which extend the subject range of the ARIADNE infrastructure, and take us into item level aggregation, as reported in Deliverables D4.2 and D4.4.

Finally, we have continued to support the ARIADNE portal, migrating the indices from ElasticSearch to the open source application OpenSearch, and adding several enhancements to the portal interface.

¹ <https://ariadne-portal-staging.d4science.org/>; <https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

2. Introduction and Objectives

The deliverable reports work undertaken in Work package 5 under Tasks 5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 5.4, 5.5 and 5.7 during the final 12 months of the project, providing an update to D5.3, and assessing what has been accomplished during the lifetime of the project. The final DMP produced within Task 5.6 is reported in D5.5. Related activity has been reported in D4.3 and D4.4.

The overall aim of WP5 has been to maintain and extend the ARIADNE Data infrastructure (ADI). This leads to three objectives:

- Keeping the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure up-to-date.
- Extending the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure to other sectors.
- Keeping the liaisons with other Catalogues, including the future EOSC catalogue of services.

The ARIADNE Data Infrastructure (ADI) was developed during the first ARIADNE infrastructure project, with funding from the European Commission under Framework Programme 7 for the period 2013-2017.² ARIADNE's goal was to provide open access to Europe's archaeological heritage and to overcome the fragmentation of digital repositories, placed in different countries and compiled in different languages (Niccolucci and Richards 2019).

Integration was achieved using state-of-the-art ICT and open data standards, creating the ARIADNE Knowledge Base with advanced search functionalities and services to use and re-use data.³ Innovative vocabulary mapping techniques have brought interoperability to a huge and heterogenous collection of texts, drawings, images, videos, 3D models and maps. By the end of the original ARIADNE project we had succeeded in cataloguing over 1.7m archaeological datasets, recorded and managed according to the FAIR principles (Aloia et al. 2017). At the time of writing over 3.3 million resources have now been integrated in ARIADNEplus, with an additional 0.5 million in the workflow.

ARIADNEplus has built upon the success of ARIADNE, **extending** its scope in a number of dimensions, covering the domains served and the users addressed:

- The **geographic coverage**, which in ARIADNE already reached almost all European regions, by integrating in the ARIADNEplus Infrastructure a greater number of archaeological partners and giving particular attention to areas where the coverage was less intensive, particularly in southern and eastern Europe (Figure 1).
- The **disciplinary coverage**, which in ARIADNE included mainly excavation data and a few specialist topics such as, for example, dendrochronology, by integrating in the new ARIADNEplus Infrastructure data produced by palaeoanthropology, bioarchaeology, environmental archaeology as well as the results of scientific analyses, such as material sciences, dating and so on, and those related to standing structures (Figure 2).
- The **time-span** considered, pushing back the earliest datasets included, by incorporating palaeoanthropology, and forwards the end-date until recent times, e.g. including industrial archaeology and Cold War archaeology; in practice covering the full time-span of the human presence on Earth.

² <http://legacy.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

³ <http://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

- The **depth of database integration**, exploiting the potential of well-structured datasets such as databases, for which the interoperability has been extended to item level (in ARIADNE implemented only experimentally), and archaeological Geographic Information Systems (GIS), for which integration has been achieved through the introduction of dedicated services, going beyond mere digital maps and overcoming incompatible reference systems.
- The **integration of text datasets** by extending the use of Text Mining through Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Named Entity Recognition (NER), previously applied only experimentally.
- The **research community** involved. ARIADNEplus has made contact with the majority of all researchers and professionals (particularly important in this domain where research and heritage management often go hand in hand), and addressed the needs of computer-aware archaeologists. Building on new partnerships in Japan and the Americas ARIADNEplus has begun to have an impact on the broader international research community.
- The **service portfolio** offered to users, incorporating more advanced tools for digital analysis and interpretation in ARIADNEplus.

Figure 1: Extension of geographic coverage from ARIADNE to ARIADNEplus

Figure 2. How ARIADNEplus extends its integration scope in time, space and content

This deliverable reports on how far these objectives have been met over the lifetime of the project.

Section 3 defines the ADI update procedure for both old and new partners. Section 4 discusses the data cleansing procedures. Section 5 describes how the current content of the ADI, inherited from ARIADNE, is being updated and how new data sets are being added, using the AO-Cat (which was described in D4.1). Section 6 discusses enhancements to the AO-Cat since M36 and the addition of VREs to the infrastructure, whilst Section 7 discusses collaboration with related initiatives and cross-discipline interoperability issues with other catalogues, and compatibility with the nascent EOSC catalogue. Finally, Section 8 concludes and addresses future plans.

3. Definition of the update procedure of the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure. Task 5.1 (NA4.1)

Task leader: UoY-ADS

This task was responsible for defining the most appropriate pipeline for updating the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure, i.e. the pipeline of actions to execute. As previously reported in D5.2 and D5.3, in ARIADNEplus we adopted an improved Data Model (The AO-Cat) developed in WP4. This had the consequence that data mappings could be simplified, but all the existing data aggregated during ARIADNE had to be re-processed to reach compliance with AO-Cat (see D4.1).

Therefore, with the agreement that all partners would need to map their data to the AO-Cat from scratch, we defined a single pipeline for both existing and new data suppliers, although existing Getty AAT and Period0 mappings have been re-used where possible (see Section 4).

From M18, we also added a process whereby partners were able to supply data updates, with a new timestamp, and this can be appended to their existing datasets rather than having to reload these in their entirety. This has now been used by several partners, including UoY-ADS, and our Associate partner ROCEEH.

Aggregation priorities were defined in Tasks 4.4 and 12.5 and we have also distinguished between those partners with large data sets who need to undertake a full 3M mapping to the AO-Cat and use the automated tools for aggregation, or those with small datasets which may be manually entered using the Fast Cat tool. These tools were described in D4.1.

A simplified version of the aggregation procedure is shown in Figure 3. In practice, there are also quality control checks at each stage in the pipeline. The D4Science Redmine helpdesk is used for partner support, with tickets corresponding to the technical partner supporting each step of the procedure. Experience with the test data has shown that it is an iterative rather than entirely linear process and that stages may need to be repeated before they are completed. For example, the 3M mapping process is a useful mechanism in forcing partners to think about their data in relation to the AO-Cat, and may lead to a need for re-supply of the data.

The aggregation procedure is described in more detail, but in an accessible manner, in the Data Aggregation Pipeline User Guide. Since M18, this has been through several updates to reflect changes to the AO-Cat and it is now in Version 2.4, dated May 2022 (Bardi et al 2022). In response to feedback from archaeological partners we also published an abbreviated version containing just the core information.

Figure 3: Simplified flowchart showing the update procedure.

During the first phase of ARIADNEplus, the partners in the aggregation task force used a shared Google sheet dashboard to define the specific stages and to enter dates as stages were completed. This was later replaced by a new software tool, **Activity Dash**, developed by FORTH as part of T14.1. This has been integrated within D4Science so that all partners can access those tasks for which they have permission, using their existing authentication credentials (Figure 4). The Activity Dash tool tracks several processes (activities) of a workflow, which might or might not be executed in a certain order. It also:

- provides workflow and activity management,
- offers a collaborative environment,
- provides reliable notification means for stakeholders to be updated of any changes on workflow activities they are interested in,
- is a reference point for stakeholders.

Name	Description	Completeness	Owner	Avatar
IAA - Survey of Israel Archive	Aggregation of Israel Antiquities Authority (IAA) survey of Israel archive	40%	Achille Felicetti	
Revised Template Workflow (Dec 2022)	Aggregation of the collections of a provider; adding public launch stage	0%	Julian Richards	
British School of Athens - aggregation of Collection Events database	581 records with information about fieldwork event archives held by BSA	12.5%	Julian Richards	
INP Chronicle of Archaeological Research Reports	Aggregation of fieldwork reports for Romania	33.33%	Julian Richards	
OAEW (ACDH-DH) collections	Aggregation of 5 collections from ARCHE (42861 items)	33.33%	Julian Richards	
Archaeological Institute of Zagreb	Database of archaeological sites in Croatia	5%	Achille Felicetti	
MIBACT data	Aggregation of MIBACT data	40%	Achille Felicetti	
Template Workflow for reloads	Abbreviated workflow where mappings have already been done	0%	Julian Richards	
ROAD updated reloads	Abbreviated workflow where mappings have all been done	60%	Julian Richards	

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Buttons: OPEN, CLONE, EXPORT TO FILE, Edit Mode, Delete Mode

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Figure 4: Screenshot of the Activity Dash 'dashboard', showing workflows in progress, December 2022. The percentage completed for each workflow is shown in an easily visualised format.

Nonetheless, and despite a number of software tools to monitor progress, regular online meetings of the aggregation task force, with representatives of UoY-ADS, PIN, CNR, FORTH, USW and with attendance by SND, have been essential to bring team members together to review progress, prioritise activities, and discuss those issues which have inevitably arisen, given the idiosyncrasies of partner data. The task force has met every two to three weeks, and at the time of writing has held 44 meetings over the lifetime of the project.

4. Data cleansing. Task 5.2 (NA4.2) Task leader: USW

This task addresses the issue of cleansing the data provided by partners, including mapping of subject terms to the Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT). It also covers the use of Period0 to provide absolute dates for named archaeological periods, as defined by partners, and the Year Spans tool to clean period information. The activity is carried out automatically whenever possible, not excluding manual intervention and revision by content providers.

4.1 Subject mapping

The Getty AAT provides identifiers and terms to describe cultural heritage concepts. Getty vocabularies including the AAT are [made available as Linked Open Data](#) (LOD), so each concept in the thesaurus has a unique identifier in the form of a URI (e.g. <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300211545> is the identifier of the concept "penannular brooches"). The AAT contains over 58,000 concepts. Continuing with the strategy adopted in the ARIADNE project, ARIADNEplus is using the AAT as a central hub for scalable interconnection of local subject vocabularies. Data providers are required to provide a set of mappings from their own local 'native' subject vocabulary (all terms used to describe subjects within their own metadata) to Getty AAT concepts. The aim is to identify subject mappings from native source terms/concepts to AAT concepts that are likely to be useful to assist subsequent browsing and searching of the data, improving recall and precision in searching, and to enhance the potential for multilingual interoperability and cross search of the aggregated data records.

4.1.1 Vocabulary Matching Tool

During the first ARIADNE project, a Vocabulary Matching Tool (VMT) was created by USW to assist data providers with creating consistent mappings between their native subject vocabulary concepts and those of the Getty AAT. This tool has been rewritten and improved in the early stages of ARIADNEplus, the new version retaining compatibility with the output format of the first version thus ensuring we could reuse any of the existing mappings already previously created. The [Vocabulary Matching Tool](#) (Figure 5) is a browser-based application with no user installation or configuration requirements, and has been deployed within the ARIADNEplus D4Science web infrastructure. It has a multilingual user interface – at the time of writing the current UI languages supported are German, English, Spanish, French, Italian and Dutch. Users can search and browse the AAT structure, viewing the hierarchical context and scope of each concept to make a far better-informed match than relying on terms alone.

The type of match between the local source concept and the target AAT concept will be one of the possible SKOS mapping properties as defined by the [SKOS reference document](#). There is an associated [online help page](#) with further instructions and general usage guidance to assist users. The tool and its operation are also described in the Data Aggregation Pipeline User Guide document (Bardi et al. 2020).

Vocabulary Matching Tool

English

Source Concept		Match ...	Target Concept	Suggest	Delete Row
Identifier	Label		Filter column...		
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ABATTOIR	en Exact Match	slaughterhouses	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ABBEY	en Exact Match	abbeys (monasteries)	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ABBOTS SUMMER PALACE	en Close Match	summer palaces	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ABLUTIONS BLOCK	en Close Match	rest rooms	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ACADEMY SCHOOL	en Close Match	academies (buildings)	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ACCIDENT HOSPITAL	en Close Match	hospitals (buildings for health facility)	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ACCOMMODATION BRIDGE	en Close Match	bridges (built works)	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ACCOMMODATION HUT	en Close Match	huts (houses)	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ACCUMULATOR HOUSE	en Close Match	power plant buildings (utilities buildi...	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ACETONE FACTORY	en Close Match	factories (structures)	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ACID WORKS	en Close Match	chemical plants	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ACTIVITY CENTRE	en Close Match	athletic clubs	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ADIT	en Close Match	mine shafts	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ADMIRALTY SIGNAL ESTABLISHM...	en Close Match	signal towers (elevated structures)	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ADMIRALTY SIGNAL STATION	en Close Match	signal houses	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ADMISSION HOSPITAL	en Close Match	hospitals (buildings for health facility)	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ADULTERINE CASTLE	en Broad Match	castles (fortifications)	Q	⊖

3979 rows

FIRST PREV 1 2 3 4 5 NEXT LAST

IMPORT JSON EXPORT JSON EXPORT CSV + ADD NEW ROW CLEAR ROWS SHOW HELP

Created by University of South Wales

ARIADNEplus is a Horizon 2020 project funded by the European Commission (Grant Agreement No 823914)

This application retrieves some information originating from Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT)® which is made available under the ODC Attribution License. See <http://vocab.getty.edu/> for further details.

Figure 5: The Vocabulary Matching Tool, illustrating the ability to define match types including Exact Match, Close Match, and Broad Match between source concepts in partners' native vocabularies and target concepts in the Getty AAT.

4.1.2 AAT mappings created

Mappings are inherently reusable as they describe semantic relationships between persistent concepts relating to the domain but are not restricted in scope to a particular dataset. Therefore, in the first instance 6,400+ existing vocabulary mappings from the preceding ARIADNE project were reused. These were then revised and supplemented as appropriate to account for changes and additions in the interim period; new mappings were also produced by the new ARIADNEplus data providers.

Provider	Country	Description	Mappings
AIAC	Italy	(FASTI mappings from ARIADNE I) AIAC also use Getty AAT terms directly in their dataset	129
ARUP: AIS-CR	Czech Republic	AMCR - bilingual – includes mappings for Czech and English terms	2,500
ASU	United States	tDAR CGRNM keywords mapped to AAT	67
AU	Denmark	DIME database + Danish sites and monuments	425
BSA	Greece	British School in Athens	22
CARARE	Ireland	European CARARE Network	486
CENIEH	Spain	National Center for Research on Human Evolution, CENIEH	692
CNRS-MASA	France	PACTOLS to AAT mappings	566
DAI	Germany	Books (from ARIADNE I) Collections (from ARIADNE I) Inscription (from ARIADNE I) Monuments (from ARIADNE I) Multi-part monuments (from ARIADNE I) Topographic objects (from ARIADNE I)	17 11 19 176 108 55
DANS-KNAW	Netherlands	DANS-DCCD (from ARIADNE I) DANS-EASY (from ARIADNE I) PAN (PAS equivalent)	336 114 162
FI	Iceland	tegund hlutverk	210
HNM	Hungary	MNM-NOK site types. Bilingual mappings	232
IAA	Israel	Israel Antiquities Authority	6
IAVP	Romania	Dobruja site types	26
INFN	Italy	Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare	6
INRAP	France	PACTOLS to AAT (from ARIADNE I)	1,814

Provider	Country	Description	Mappings
KHM-UO	Norway	Artefact terminology (bilingual, English/Norwegian) Find categories (bilingual, English/Norwegian) normertegenstander	1,228 136 411
LNEC	Portugal	LNEC created a bilingual (English/Portuguese) subject vocabulary, mappings are from English terms to AAT concepts	160
MIBAC-ICCU	Italy	PICO (from ARIADNE I) ICCU (from ARIADNE I)	144 1,304
MISANU	Serbia	Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts	17
NARA	Japan	New Japanese controlled vocabulary mapped to Getty AAT	1,654
NIAM-BAS	Bulgaria	(from ARIADNE I) revised and extended	238
OEAW	Austria	DFMROE (from ARIADNE I) FH (from ARIADNE I) UK-POOL (from ARIADNE I) UK-THUNAU (from ARIADNE I) ARCHE-AAT	7 10 16 4 66
PAS-UK	United Kingdom	Culture Land use Manufacturing technique Material Surface treatment	7 7 8 28 12
PP	Greece	Materials SiteTypes Species AdminRegions SiteNames	54 40 138 13 353
ROCEEH	Germany	Interpretation Material Plant remains Category Human remains	13 30 2 18 16
SND	Sweden	Revised and extended version of previous mappings SHFA – Swedish Rock Art	431 132
THANADOS	Austria	THANADOS gazetteer vocabulary mappings	233

Provider	Country	Description	Mappings
UoY-ADS	United Kingdom	Building materials (from ARIADNE I)	12
		Components (from ARIADNE I)	9
		Object types (from ARIADNE I)	1,077
		HE maritime craft types (from ARIADNE I)	408
		Monument types (revised)	4,018
		PAS coins mapping	386
		HES maritime craft types	203
Wikidata	-	Multilingual terms mapped to AAT (extracted 598,584) Not included in totals here; see breakdown table below	-
ZRC-SAZU	Slovenia	ARKAS (from ARIADNE I) Supplemented with English term mappings	186
		ZBIVA (from ARIADNE I) Supplemented with English term mappings	60
		Total:	21,468

Wikidata terms mapped to AAT concepts have been extracted and converted to the same format as output by the Vocabulary Matching Tool. It is envisaged these can be used in the same way as existing native term mappings, to supplement the search vocabulary giving greater potential for multilingual search. The figures are given separately here so as not to be confused with the numbers for native vocabulary mappings created by data partners.

Language Code	Language Name	AAT mappings
ar	Arabic	23,687
bg	Bulgarian	11,446
bs	Bosnian	3,823
cs	Czech	17,946
da	Danish	14,227
de	German	44,111
el	Greek	9,265

Language Code	Language Name	AAT mappings
en	English	55,721
es	Spanish	45,496
fi	Finnish	18,097
fr	French	36,360
ga	Irish	6,212
he	Hebrew	15,646
hr	Croatian	9,051
hu	Hungarian	10,917
is	Icelandic	4,930
it	Italian	25,549
ja	Japanese	27,630
mk	Macedonian	9,693
nl	Dutch	27,259
no	Norwegian	408
pl	Polish	18,919
pt	Portuguese	28,589
ro	Romanian	11,264
ru	Russian	28,876

Language Code	Language Name	AAT mappings
sk	Slovak	8,443
sl	Slovenian	7,635
sq	Albanian	3,479
sr	Serbian	18,980
sv	Swedish	23,601
tr	Turkish	13,299
uk	Ukrainian	18,025
	Total:	598,584

4.2 Period mapping

[PeriodO](#) is a multilingual gazetteer of scholarly definitions for describing historical and archaeological named periods. It comprises a series of 'authorities' (lists of named periods) where each individual period definition is associated with a particular spatial coverage and a start date and end date, plus other metadata including a bibliographic reference for the source of the term. Periods and authorities have 'permalink' identifiers (URIs) so they can be clearly and unambiguously referenced - e.g. the identifier <http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr4scv9> uniquely defines a period with the label "Haut Moyen Âge" (High Middle Ages) within the authority <http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr4> "PACTOLS chronology periods used in DOLIA data".

PeriodO can accommodate multiple perspectives regarding the dates for a named period for the same spatial extents as shown in the following table, therefore, it is important for ARIADNEplus to make explicit the meaning and intended spatial coverage of named periods where they exist in data records.

Identifier	Label(s)	Source	Spatial Coverage	Start	End
http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0qhb66cqqg	Bronze Age	ARIADNE Data Collection (2015)	Britain	2900 BCE	1801 BCE*

Identifier	Label(s)	Source	Spatial Coverage	Start	End
http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0gjgrs6qb2	Bronze Age	Portable Antiquities Scheme (2003)	UK	2350 BCE	801 BCE
http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0kh9ds7q8m	Bronze Age	Historic England Periods List (2014)	UK	2600 BCE	700 BCE
http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0zj6g8rbvk	Bronze Age	ARENA Portal (2004)	UK	2500 BCE	700 BCE
http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0xxt6tfv6h	Bronze Age	Scottish Archaeological Periods & Ages (2018)	Scotland	2200 BCE	800 BCE

*entered value is 3801 BP (2000) – likely intended value is 2801 BP (2000)

Named periods are defined with reference to periods existing within PeriodO authorities. In the first instance, the existing published period authorities used in the first ARIADNE project were reused; data partners subsequently created and published additional authorities. Period definitions produced by data partners are shown in the following table. Some data partners included dates directly within their data without reference to an external authority, so data partners do not all necessarily have a corresponding PeriodO authority.

Provider (contact)	Description	Periods
ARIADNE I	ARIADNE data collection http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0qhb66	663
AIAC	FASTI - Home. 2004 http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p06v8w4 AIAC report that they use absolute dates in their underlying data	212
ARUP	AMCR Periods Vocabulary http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0wctqt	142
ASU	David R. Abbott. Extensive and Long-Term Specialization: Hohokam Ceramic Production in the Phoenix Basin, Arizona. 2009-07. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02kdd9	14 6

Provider (contact)	Description	Periods
	David R. Abbott et al. Calculating Hohokam Domestic Architecture Building Costs to Test an Environmental Model of Architectural Changes. 2019-04. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p03dr36	
CARARE	Archaeological periods for the island of Ireland http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p06hps8	11
CENIEH	Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana, CENIEH. 2021. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0h9ttq	142
DANS-KNAW	Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed. Het Archeologisch Basisregister (ABR). 1992. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0pqptc	53
HNM	No separate PeriodO collection; Hungarian periods are included in the aggregated collection "ARIADNE Data Collection. 2015." http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0qhb66 (With spatial coverage http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q28 , Hungary)	32
IAVP	Romanian Dobruja Periodisation http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02kbfm	24
INP	terms extracted from the 'Treaty of Romanian History'	-
INRAP	INRAP: Institut National de Recherches Archéologiques Préventives. PACTOLS chronology periods used in DOLIA data. 2021. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr4	123
KHM-UO	Norsk arkeologisk leksikon. 2005. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p04h98q	28
LNEC	DB-HERITAGE project. DB-HERITAGE historical periods. 2021. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0cwscs	20
NARA	Agency for Cultural Affairs, Government of Japan. Exhibition of Excavations in the Japanese Archipelago 2020. 2020. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0g8mw8	40
NIAM-BAS	No separate PeriodO collection; Bulgarian periods are included in the aggregated collection "ARIADNE Data Collection. 2015." http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0qhb66 (With spatial coverage http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q219 , Bulgaria)	33

Provider (contact)	Description	Periods
OEAW	No separate PeriodO collection; Austrian periods are included in the aggregated collection "ARIADNE Data Collection. 2015." http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0qhb66 (With spatial coverage http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q40 , Austria)	31
PAS-UK	Portable Antiquities Scheme. Periods used on the database. 2003. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0gjgrs	31
PP	PP prepared a draft spreadsheet list of cultural periods with PeriodO references.	-
ROCEEH	ROCEEH Out of Africa Database (ROAD) http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0s2rwk	134
SND	No separate PeriodO collection; Swedish periods are included in the aggregated collection "ARIADNE Data Collection. 2015." http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0qhb66 (With spatial coverage http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q34 , Sweden) SHFA (rock Art): Historiska museet. Sök i samlingarna (beta). 2011. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0vn2fr	47 32
THANADOS	The Anthropological and Archaeological Database of Sepultures. 2022 http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0cwwzn	19
UoY-ADS	Heritage Data. Linked Data Vocabularies for Cultural Heritage. 2014. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0kh9ds ScAPA Scottish Archaeological Periods & Ages http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0xxt6t	42 176
ZRC-SAZU	No separate PeriodO collection; Slovenian periods are included in the aggregated collection "ARIADNE Data Collection. 2015." http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0qhb66 (With spatial coverage http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q215 , Slovenia)	31
	Total:	2,086

4.3 Year Spans Tool

The purpose of using PeriodO in ARIADNEplus is different to the use of AAT mappings - rather than aligning data to common identifiers, PeriodO is utilised in a data enrichment stage to enrich records already indexed with named periods (such as “Bronze Age”, “Iron Age” etc.) where the dates associated with these periods are not already made explicit in the input data - determining the intended meaning of named periods in terms of absolute start/end years so that the records can be compared by date and aggregated according to a common timeline. However, in addition to named periods there are occasions where records refer to periods in other forms:

- A span of years (e.g. “1000 BC to 1785 AD”).
- Year with tolerance (e.g. “1666”, “1485+5-10”, “1540±9”)
- A decade (e.g. “the 1920s”)
- Ordinal named or numbered centuries (e.g. “circa C15”, “Early fifteenth century”)
- A span of centuries (e.g. “Late 15th-Mid 17th century”)

Terms of this kind do not exist in PeriodO, and where the start/end years are not easily derived in a consistent way this would prevent these records being compared by date. The terms sometimes have additional prefixes and suffixes (e.g. “circa”, “early”, “AD”, “BCE”). A further complication is multilingual variations in the way such terms may be expressed.

USW have created a bulk data processing tool to resolve this situation - deriving suitable start/end years from such textual strings. Due to the ARIADNEplus workflow and restriction not to make any changes to the existing records provided by the data provider, it was necessary to make a modified version of the tool functionality to import the ‘raw’ XML data records from the data provider and to supplement any year span values present with new derived start/end year elements, prior to the records being ingested. The example below shows a brief explanatory extract of the output of the tool – a record having an existing “dcterms:temporal” element describing a particular year span value has been supplemented with new “minYear” and “maxYear” sibling elements explicitly expressing the start/end years as separate xsd:gYear values.

```
<record type="record">
  <dc:title>ST. MARTIN'S CHURCH</dc:title>
  <dc:creator>Exeter City Council</dc:creator>
  <dc:subjectPeriod>
    <dc:subject>CHURCH</dc:subject>
    <dcterms:temporal>850 - 1068</dcterms:temporal>
    <minYear xsi:type="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#gYear">0850</minYear>
    <maxYear xsi:type="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#gYear">1068</maxYear>
  </dc:subjectPeriod>
  . . .
</record>
```

Following initial testing and adjustment the tool was applied to ‘real’ input data using 5 XML files originating from UoY-ADS. The files typically contained a mixture of named periods and year spans. In most cases, named periods were not processed as they would be present in the associated PeriodO collection anyway, so the dates should subsequently be populated through that route. As this was

legacy data that did not necessarily conform to the period controlled vocabulary currently in use in the source organisation, some special cases were made to accommodate named period terms which, although they did not occur in the associated PeriodO collection, occurred frequently enough to warrant handling e.g. the term *INTER WAR* was considered to mean the period from 1919 to 1938.

The tool takes only a few seconds to process each data file in turn. The results of the bulk data processing work undertaken are shown in the following table:

Input file name	Temporal records	Processed	Not handled
ariadne_324.xml	20,113	18,982	1,131
ariadne_328.xml	59,278	59,278	0
ariadne_1054.xml	971	971	0
ariadne_1970.xml	20,310	20,310	0
ariadne_1972.xml	16,689	16,689	0
Totals	117,361	116,230	1,131

Investigating the “not handled” records (in ADS collection 324) – the majority were for the named period *COLD WAR* – which is actually present in the associated PeriodO collection in any case, so the appropriate dates will subsequently be populated through that route. The remainder (50 records) were using the term *PRE-WORLD WAR I*, which was not considered specific enough to impose an absolute date span due to uncertainty over exactly what it meant.

5. Feeding content into the ARIADNEplus infrastructure. Tasks 5.3 and 5.4 (NA4.3 and NA4.4) Task leader: CNR-ISTI

This section describes the activities of the Tasks 5.3 (NA4.3 - Updating the current content of the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure (ADI)) and 5.4 (NA4.4 - Ingesting data into the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure) led by CNR-ISTI.

The main objectives of the tasks are:

1. Definition of the aggregation workflow
2. Execution of aggregation activities.

5.1 Definition of the aggregation workflow

The previous ARIADNE infrastructure aggregated information about archaeological datasets, described according to the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM). With the adoption of the ARIADNEplus Data Model (AO-Cat) developed in WP4 of the ARIADNEplus project, the data aggregated during the ARIADNE project and already publicly available via the ARIADNE portal were re-processed to achieve compliance with AO-Cat.

Following the decisions taken in Task 5.1 – Definition of the update procedure of the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure (NA4.1), Task 5.3 has been planned to collect from scratch all the records from the ARIADNEplus partners and transform them according to the AO-Cat model by applying new 3M mappings (defined in the context of Task 4.2 – Mapping dataset metadata to the ARIADNEplus Data Model (NA3.2)).

The complete re-aggregation of content with the new aggregation infrastructure based on the D-Net framework toolkit (developed and operated in WP12) smoothly addresses the two main issues identified in the Description of the Action:

1. Filling the gaps (Sub-task 5.3.1): due to the gap of about two years between ARIADNE and ARIADNEplus, the content available in the ARIADNE infrastructure does not include new and updated records that are available from the data providers.
2. Regular updates (Sub-task 5.3.2): the D-Net framework toolkit natively supports the incremental aggregation of records available via online endpoints (provided incremental collection is supported by the endpoints) and the aggregation workflows can be scheduled to run at given intervals in time. Scheduling is configurable with cron expressions⁴ that can be different for each partner (e.g. DANS data can be aggregated each Monday morning; UoY-ADS data on the 1st of each month). The aggregation schedule is, therefore, agreed with each partner, based on the update frequency of the content on their endpoints.

⁴ Cron expression: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cron#CRON_expression

Thanks to this decision, there was no need to define separate procedures for the aggregation of “old” and “new” content. Therefore, the main objective of both Tasks 5.3 and 5.4 in the first project period was to define the aggregation pipeline (or workflow), i.e. the sequence of steps to be performed for the aggregation of metadata records of the ARIADNEplus partners.

For the definition of the aggregation workflow, an iterative approach has been adopted, where refinements to the different steps have been applied based on requirements, suggestions and feedback from WP4 and WP12. The description of the workflow has been defined in the document “Data Aggregation Pipeline: User Guide” (Bardi et al 2020). The workflow comprises the flows depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6: The aggregation workflow

The flows identified as 1, 2, 3, 4 and 6 in Figure 6 are intended to feed the knowledge base (implemented with an instance of GraphDB⁵):

1. *Ingestion of XML records of the provider.* Records are collected, transformed into AO-Cat by applying a dedicated 3M mapping, and fed into the knowledge base.
2. *Enrichment with Getty AAT subjects⁶.* The subject mapping to Getty AAT (see [Section 4.1](#)) is transformed into RDF by applying the 3M mapping 875 and fed into the knowledge base. As a result, the knowledge base contains the correspondences between native subjects and terms within the Getty AAT vocabulary.
3. *Enrichment with PeriodO.* The PeriodO datasets defined by the provider (see [Section 4.2](#)) are ingested into the knowledge base and used to generate explicit ‘aocat:has_period’ properties.
4. *Feed the staging knowledge base.* In order to support the providers with checking the content before it is made publicly available, the push on the knowledge base initially targets a “staging” instance. Specific SPARQL INSERT statements are executed (4a) in order to enrich records with AO-Cat properties that are not explicitly available in the mapped records, but that are statically known or can be inferred from other properties or related records (e.g. inheritance of properties of a dataset from its collection). Step 4a also allows the aggregation manager to address possible peculiarities in the data that could complicate the automatic feeding to the portal.
5. *Feed the staging ARIADNEplus portal.* For each set of records ingested via step 1, a procedure reads the corresponding triples and builds json records to feed the index server that serves the ARIADNEplus portal. The procedure includes in the json records the properties that have been added by the other steps (2-3-4a)
6. *Feed the public knowledge base.* This flow is executed if the provider successfully completed the content checking on the staging knowledge base and portal.
7. *Feed the public ARIADNEplus portal.* The flow applies the same procedure as step 5, using the public instances of the knowledge base and portal instead of the staging instances.

Steps 4 and 5 support the quality checks of content and can be bypassed once the input format of the records and the 3M mappings of a provider are stable, so that it will be possible to automatically update the knowledge graph and the ARIADNEplus portal with updated and new records without human intervention. If necessary, steps 4 and 5 might be reactivated for a given source (e.g. because the provider upgraded the information system and wants to perform extensive checks before the data supplied by the new system goes public).

Based on the information collected from the providers, among the 10 providers offering APIs from which it is possible to collect metadata in an automatic way (in incremental or refresh mode), two can be regularly updated every week, three every six months, one every four months, one every year, while three were not sure (Bardi 2022).

⁵ GraphDB: <http://graphdb.ontotext.com/>

⁶ Getty AAT: <https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/index.html>

5.2 Execution of aggregation activities

The aggregation activities have been planned to support the work and match the timeline of WP12 (for the development and deployment of the services of the aggregative infrastructure and new versions of the portal) and WP4 (for the preparation of 3M mappings).

Phase 1: testing the aggregative infrastructure with UoY-ADS records

The content update on the new A+ infrastructure has been tested with records provided by the ADS. This phase informed WP12 about requirements and needed to be fulfilled with the integration of additional tools and services for data processing and curation that were not foreseen in the DoA. This phase was completed in June 2020.

Phase 2: aggregation of records of ARIADNE partners according to the pipeline defined in T5.1

This phase started at the end of June 2020 and by December 2022 resulted in the aggregation of 38 providers, for a total of 182 million explicit triples (387 million including the inferred triples) in the public knowledge base and 3.3 million records in the public portal.

Aggregation details by partner/source are shown in the tables below, including both records per partner/dataset on the public portal, and records per partner/dataset on the staging portal. Most of the data sets have been re-aggregated and re-published on the portals several times due to one or more of the following reasons:

- updates to the AO-Cat ontology,
- updates to the portals,
- fine tuning of the mappings,
- improvements to the enrichment step,
- updated input data from the provider,
- changes to the provider's endpoint.

Aggregated records available in the public portal as of December 2022.⁷ The available records in the ARIADNEplus portal is expected to continue to grow beyond the end of the funded project, thanks to additional providers who joined the aggregation queue, the agreed scheduled updates, and additional dataset collections from partners (with an asterisk in the table).

Provider	# records in public portal (approx.)
ADS	1.1M
British Museum	945K
Historic Environment Scotland	334K
AIS CR	230K
Nara	140K

⁷ For the most up-to-date numbers refer to the “filter by publisher” on the ARIADNEplus portal (<https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/search?q=>).

Provider	# records in public portal (approx.)
DANS*	99K
HNM	63K
CEIPAC	57K
Inrap	37K
Swedish Rock Art	25K
THANADOS	23K
National Heritage Institute - Romania	18K
International Association for Classical Archaeology	14K
The Institute of Archaeology, Iceland	10K
ZRC SAZU	8.7K
Aarhus University (DIME)	8.6K
CENIEH*	8K
Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities	7.5K
The Finnish Heritage Agency	3K
IDACOR	2.5K
Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	2K
LNEC	1K
SND	500
OeAW*	300
Center for Digital Antiquity	171
Institute of Archaeology Vasile Parvan	136
The Cyprus Institute*	110
INFN	43
ICCD (MIBAC)*	22
University of Innsbruck	19
MASA*	9
University of Patras	3

6. Extending the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure scope. Task 5.5 (NA4.5) Task leader: CNR-ISTI

During the project lifetime, the Consortium members in charge of Task 5.5 provided the ARIADNE Catalogue ontology (AO-Cat, as it is named within the Consortium) as a pivotal language for representing the data resources shared by the project partners through the ARIADNE Research Infrastructure. AO-Cat derives from the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM for short), employed in the predecessor ARIADNE project to model archaeological resources, and from the PARTHENOS Entities Model (PEM), employed in the PARTHENOS project to model the resources managed by a Research Infrastructure.

In its initial version, AO-Cat was a contraction of the ACDM driven by the conceptualization underlying the PEM. In addition, AO-Cat inherited from the PEM its tight relation to the CRM, which is used to represent any aspect of archaeological resources not covered by the ACDM or the PEM.

During the first 18 months of the project, AO-Cat evolved in order to accommodate the representational requirements collected while aggregating the first collections, mainly provided by the Archaeology Data Service (ADS for short) of the University of York. Based on the long-lasting experience of the ADS, these collections were chosen as representative of the complexity to be found in the data sets to be aggregated

During the following 18 months, AO-Cat was modified further to cope with more specific requirements, namely the representation of uncertainty in spatial regions and that of digital images associated with archaeological records.

In the last year of the project, no significant change was required to the AO-Cat to support the aggregation process in an adequate manner, in spite of the fact that the latest additions of data sets have come from a larger number of partners than those contributing to the early phases.

Furthermore, as argued in Section 6 of Deliverable 4.4, AO-Cat has turned out to be adequate also for the representation requirements of the archaeological domains. In fact, the model provides suitable classes for high-profile description of artefacts and other archaeological objects (AO-Object), places (AO-Spatial-Region) and events (AO-Event).

In sum, the AO-Cat ontology has reached a mature level of stability and is, therefore, ready for wider usage outside the boundaries of the ARIADNEplus project. Indeed, it has been adopted by the ADS as the ontology which now supports the UK's Towards a National Collection Unpath'd Waters project, where it is used to underpin the aggregation of maritime heritage data.⁸

⁸ <https://unpathdwaters.org.uk/data-catalogue-launched/>

7. Collaborating with other Catalogues. Task 5.7 (NA4.7) Task leader: PIN

This task is responsible for collaborating and addressing cross-discipline interoperability issues with catalogues in other domains, as well as for ensuring compatibility with the future EOSC infrastructure, and with OpenAIRE. It also involves partnerships with other archaeological aggregators, developed as part of WP2, including Pelagios, ROCEEH, and THANADOS.

7.1 Collaboration with generic platforms and initiatives

The development and testing of TEXTCROWD⁹ continued in the last period of ARIADNEplus. TEXTCROWD was originally designed as a Science Demonstrators of the EOSCpilot project¹⁰ (where the ARIADNE community was represented by PIN, supported by CNR) to showcase the needs and solutions of the archaeological community in the EOSC framework. The tool was designed for the **classification** and the **annotation** of textual documents in various languages (see below), and the extraction of domain-specific entities and relationships present in the texts. The classification and annotation operations are carried out using Deep Learning techniques, a particular AI methodology implemented by means of convolutional neural networks trained to understand the linguistic meaning of the analysed texts. TEXTCROWD runs a Supervised Machine Learning algorithm (Conditional Random Fields and Neural Networks) to learn an entity recognition model from human annotated documents. The algorithm was trained with a set of about 500 manually annotated archaeological documents coming from Italian archaeological research. The Named Entity Recognition (NER) engine of TEXTCROWD is thus capable of efficiently processing streams with large amounts of documents and operating text classification and annotation on them.

Text classification consists in the automatic assignment to each analysed document of concepts deriving from one or more taxonomies and vocabularies, such as Getty AAT and FISH¹¹. The assignment is made on the basis of the topics covered or the specific content of the document. This operation makes it possible to generate and store information relating to documents in shared archives indexed by means of vocabularies, such as the ARIADNE Catalogue, and connected through the cloud, such as those of OpenAIRE Connect¹². The classification also allows the creation of additional metadata, derived from the text, such as: the authors or other people mentioned, the language of the documents, dates, places, activities and events, relevant objects and so on. TEXTCROWD neural network is also able to build short summaries to allow quick readings of the text, and to identify keywords useful for cataloguing, to make the archiving and indexing of the document even more efficient.

⁹ <https://eoscpilot.eu/science-demos/textcrowd>.

¹⁰ <https://www.eoscpilot.eu>.

¹¹ <http://www.heritage-standards.org.uk/fish-vocabularies/>.

¹² <https://connect.openaire.eu>.

Text annotation consists in identifying entities semantically relevant for specific research domains, such as archaeology or applied sciences, available in the text. This operation makes it possible to capture information relating to artefacts, biological remains, sites, people, geographical entities, time periods, activities, legal entities and organisations, extract them from the texts (e.g., from archaeological reports, excavation diaries and other similar textual documents), and encode them in a machine-readable format by means of the classes and properties of models such as CIDOC CRM or the ARIADNE AO-Cat Ontology. This allows TEXTCROWD to foster the building of semantic graphs of structured textual information, to be integrated into shared knowledge archives, such as the ARIADNE Semantic Graph¹³.

Experiments for future enhancements of TEXTCROWD have been conducted regarding the use of Transfer Learning technologies, which offer the possibility of using the knowledge acquired in a certain domain or from documents in a specific language to classify and annotate documents of other related domains or written in different languages. This would guarantee the possibility of completely agnostic tools, easy to configure and adapt, with appropriate training, for the specific purposes of any research domain.

The annotation of the archaeological documents used for TEXTCROWD training was done by means of INCEpTION¹⁴, an open-source tool set that integrates seamlessly with TEXTCROWD allowing immediate integration of annotated documents and real-time, progressive training of its NER engine by means of the annotations users define. TEXTCROWD in turn, as it is trained, provides suggestions to users through the INCEpTION interface in order to speed up and incrementally simplify annotation operations. In the last part of ARIADNEplus, the integration between the two tools has been enhanced to establish a greater synergy between them. Additionally, TEXTCROWD and INCEpTION have also been incorporated as part of the ARIADNE Lab¹⁵, the Virtual Research Environment of the ARIADNE Platform intended to provide archaeologists and scholars with a set of tools to aggregate the data of the ARIADNE infrastructure and analyse them in a collaborative and framework.

7.2 Collaboration with the EOSC and OpenAIRE environments

PIN, CNR and INFN, are strongly involved in the global development of EOSC and have kept ARIADNEplus partners informed about the progress of all these activities. In addition, UoY-ADS, DANS-KNAW and CNR are also partners in SSHOC¹⁶, where UoY-ADS represented the Heritage Science community and was responsible for a deliverable addressing the challenges of FAIR data in the heritage science and archaeological communities. This also ensures useful cross-fertilisation between ARIADNEplus and EOSC.

The development and enhancement of the THESPIAN platform (Tools for HEritage Science Processing, Integration, and ANalysis), developed by PIN and INFN in the framework of the collaboration between

¹³ <https://graphdb.ariadne.d4science.org/>.

¹⁴ <https://inception-project.github.io>.

¹⁵ https://ariadne.d4science.org/web/ariadneplus_lab/.

¹⁶ <https://sshopencloud.eu/>.

ARIADNEplus and EOSC-Pillar¹⁷, was also carried forward in the last period of ARIADNEplus. THESPIAN comprises a set of services intended to offer facilities to the researchers of Heritage Science for the storage and efficient query of raw data and their reuse according to the FAIR principles¹⁸. THESPIAN consists of a web platform for assisted metadata generation, and a service for persistent storage of scientific data and their metadata. The tool is tailored on a metadata model based on the ARIADNEplus CRMhs application profile and in general and is designed for modelling the complex entities typical of heritage science. The use of CRMhs also makes the information fully interoperable with other CIDOC CRM ecosystem and allows its integration in existing cloud environments and extended semantic graphs, such as the semantic data cloud developed by ARIADNEplus.

The THESPIAN system is currently composed of two integrated web services. The first one is THESPIAN-MASK, a cloud-based platform able to offer a collaborative environment for the storage of metadata derived from scientific information (including analysis procedures and protocols, scientific reports etc.) together with their raw data. The tool is able to process data, results and documentation, article preprints and so forth and to encode them by means of the CRMhs and AO-Cat application profiles, for an efficient item level integration. THESPIAN-MASK is also equipped with advanced features for Linked Open Data automatic acquisition and incorporation, and is able to query remote thesauri and gazetteer (such as Getty AAT and PeriodO) for the rapid inclusion of conceptual, spatial and temporal data. Information codified by means of THESPIAN-MASK is compatible with the ARIADNEplus data framework and can be exported and aggregated in any CIDOC CRM enabled semantic platform (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: The THESPIAN-MASK interfaces for CRMhs and AO-Cat scientific data encoding.

The second service of the THESPIAN ecosystem is THESPIAN-NER, a Natural Language Processing (NLP) tool for NER operations using two deep learning models based on different techniques, namely a

¹⁷ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu>.

¹⁸ <https://ch.cloud.cnaf.infn.it>.

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), based model and Transformer model. THESPIAN-NER, which extends TEXTCROWD and was part of the EOSC-Pillar project, allows users to automatically annotate either archaeological documents or scientific reports written in Italian by identifying and labelling relevant semantic entities in the text, according to the CRMhs ontology. The service is based upon two ad-hoc trained neural network: ArcheoNER, for processing archaeological texts, and hsNER, for Scientific Reports of Analysis on Cultural Heritage. These two models were trained using transfer learning techniques to classify named entities. The scientific reports employed for training refer to analysis carried out by INFN and comprising either X-Ray Fluorescence imaging (XRF) of Pictorial Artworks and Radiocarbon dating of various samples, either natural objects or artefacts. The extracted information can be exported and integrated in other semantic environments and used for building custom queries to fetch related records available on other semantic data clouds. The user interface of THESPIAN-NER is presented in Figure 8.

The screenshot displays the THESPIAN-NER interface. At the top, it reads "THESPIAN-NER - Named Entity Recognition tool for Archeology". Below this is the subtitle "Collaborative semantic enrichment of text-based datasets - Italian language version". The main area shows a text snippet with various entities highlighted in colored boxes: "primi scavi" (ACT), "dal 1748" (TSP), "Ercolano" (SIT), "sondaggi" (ACT), "Civita" (SIT), "monete" (ART), "d'epoca romana" (PRD), "nel 1754" (TSP), "nel 1763" (TSP), "un'epigrafe" (ART), "Ferdinando IV" (PER), "tempio di Iside" (ART), and "necropoli vennero" (SIT). Below the text are buttons for "Use extractive text summarisation", "Download as html", and "Download as .txt". A table below the text lists the following entities and their counts:

Timespan	Number of Timespan found in the text: 11
Artefacts	Number of Artefacts found in the text: 7
Site	Number of Site found in the text: 4
Location	Number of Location found in the text: 4
Person	Number of Person found in the text: 2
Activity	Number of Activity found in the text: 2
Period	Number of Period found in the text: 1
Organisation	Number of Organisation found in the text: 0
Biological Remains	Number of Biological Remains found in the text: 0

At the bottom left, it shows "Number of selected entities: 0".

Figure 8: The THESPIAN-NER UI for Named Entities Recognition of textual documents

Other tools and services developed by ARIADNEplus have also been kept constantly aligned and fully interoperable with the EOSC environment, especially through the D4Science platform and the Virtual Research Environments by which the ARIADNEplus platform is operated. Some ARIADNEplus services are already shared with EOSC, including authentication and management of federated identities, interconnection of distributed infrastructures, and orchestration of distributed services. Furthermore, ARIADNEplus is also ready to make its services and tools easily available through the EOSC Marketplace¹⁹.

¹⁹ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/>.

ARIADNEplus work on digital libraries has been undertaken in collaboration with OpenAIRE, an initiative aimed at providing unlimited, barrier free, open access to research outputs financed by public funding in Europe. OpenAIRE services are part of the EOSC ecosystem, and its Community Gateway for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage²⁰ offers a view of the OpenAIRE Research Graph²¹ including literature, datasets, software, other research products, and projects, all linked to each other relative to the domain of Digital Humanities. OpenAIRE users can discover scientific outputs and browse their discipline-specific graph, monitor Open Science statistics over time, and by accessing Zenodo²² also deposit/publish new products by assigning them to this community. OpenAIRE Research Graph is one of the authoritative sources for the European Open Science Cloud.

As part of the integration activities with the OpenAIRE framework, the ARIADNEplus data space has been connected with repositories of scientific publications provided by OpenAIRE through a text mining relational citation matching algorithm developed by the OpenAIRE community, in order to establish links between the archaeological data in ARIADNEplus and the information present in external digital libraries. This is implemented by exploiting OpenAIRE and its open access digital archives and the links to individual journals such as *Internet Archaeology* or *Archeologia e Calcolatori*. The text mining algorithm was refined during the last period of the project, in order to maximise the accuracy in locating publications precisely. It has also been made able to format the information in a way compatible with the ARIADNEplus triplestore, to further increase the integration of the extracted and encoded information.

7.3 Collaboration with other archaeological and anthropological aggregators

ARIADNEplus continued to analyse the technology developed by the Pelagios community and its Digital Humanities initiatives aimed at providing linkages between online resources documenting the past²³. The Recogito tool²⁴, an online platform developed by Pelagios, allows the establishment of relationships between textual fragments or areas of images, and geographical and spatial entities, in order to define geographic maps enriched with textual and semantic content. Additionally, Recogito fosters collaborative document annotation providing a personal workspace where scholars can upload, collect and organise source materials - texts, images and tabular data - and work together in a joint activity of content definition and interpretation. Annotated data are made available on the Web as Linked Open Data.

Previous collaboration with Pelagios included the definition of a series of case studies spanning various disciplines, in which archaeology, cultural and digital heritage could interact and become interoperable both at the level of data and as regards tools and services. In the last period of our project, Recogito has been evaluated by PIN in all its functions and the data model on which the tool relies, has been aligned at the conceptual level with the ontologies and models released by

²⁰ <https://dh-ch.openaire.eu>.

²¹ <https://graph.openaire.eu/>.

²² <https://zenodo.org/>.

²³ <https://pelagios.org>.

²⁴ <https://recogito.pelagios.org>.

ARIADNEplus, in order to establish cross compatibility between the generated information. Some tests have been also carried out to make Pelagios interoperable with TEXTCROWD and THESPIAN-NER in order to produce a complete platform for annotating resources of any kind. The tests also gave excellent results in terms of implementation, demonstrating that the possibility of hosting Pelagios in one of the ARIADNEplus VREs is perfectly feasible. This would allow the creation of a distributed digital platform, based on the Linked Open Data paradigm, capable of managing complex data in interdisciplinary scenarios and of providing deeper integration between spatial and textual information.

ARIADNEplus continued to work closely with the ROCEEH ("The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans") project of the Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities²⁵. The main aim of this collaboration was the acquisition and integration of the ROCEEH archives and the developing of a long-term preservation strategy for their paleoanthropological data. ROCEEH has gathered around 8,000 archaeological assemblages from approximately 1,700 localities in Africa/Eurasia and stored it in a database, called ROAD²⁶, that comprise predominantly early human cultural and biological artefacts, as well as environmental data, which have been extracted from scientific publications and excavation data (e.g. UNESCO Swabian Jura). As a result of the close collaboration between ARIADNEplus and ROCEEH, it has been possible to provide a complete and exhaustive description of the complex concepts of paleoanthropology (such as that of *assemblage* and *stratified deposit of biological object*) by means of the classes and properties provided by the AO-Cat ontology. The AO-Cat model has been used to encode ROCEEH information and to describe the paleoanthropological data in detail, allowing the integration of information about more than 1,800 sites and 10,000 assemblages of the ROAD and their publication on the ARIADNEplus infrastructure.

The collaboration with THANADOS, an Austrian anthropological and archaeological database of cemeteries and graves²⁷, has also been continuous and fruitful. THANADOS provides an open source and open access online application that intends to present all so far published archaeological and anthropological data on early medieval cemeteries in present day Austria. In the previous reporting period, THANADOS joined ARIADNEplus as an Associate Partner with the aim of integrating the THANADOS data into the ARIADNEplus infrastructure. Thus, the Mortuary Data Application Profile has been developed and adapted to act in synergy with the AO-Cat model, in order to build a complete framework allowing a proper encoding also of THANADOS data. The AO-Cat mapping enables the use of ARIADNE resource types 'Site/monument', 'Burial' and 'Artefact' to mirror the relational structure of the THANADOS database, allowing users to filter according to the level of granularity of interest to them. In turn, the Mortuary application profile can be used to encode the details of each of the unique aspects of this archaeological activity. A complete description of the Mortuary AP and the way it has been used in the framework of ARIADNEplus is available in the "Types of burial data and proposal of a Mortuary Data Application Profile for ARIADNEplus (WP4.4.14)"²⁸ internal report, and in Section 4.14 of the D4.4 deliverable.

²⁵ <http://www.roceeh.net>.

²⁶ https://www.roceeh.uni-tuebingen.de/roadweb/smarty_road_simple_search.php

²⁷ <https://thanados.net>.

²⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7252485>.

8. Conclusions

In conclusion, ARIADNEplus has had a transformational impact on the aggregation of archaeological data. We have made significant improvements to the procedures for updating and extending the ARIADNEplus infrastructure from those which were used during the first ARIADNE project, via the AO-Cat ontology (a direct subset of the CIDOC CRM), and a portal underpinned by a Linked Open Data triple store. At the time of writing this holds over 380 million triples (180 explicit and 200 inferred triples), with over 3.3 million records in the public portal, and at least another 0.5 million resources in the aggregation pipeline.

The development and testing of the new ontology and the tools and technologies to support data aggregation occupied much of our first year, in order to ensure they were fit for purpose, but by M12 we had defined a clear pipeline for adding and updating data resources (Task 5.1). Data cleansing was undertaken via an enhanced vocabulary mapping tool to facilitate the mapping of native subject terms to the Getty AAT, and collaboration with PeriodO to define period terms, as well as use of the Time Spans tool to provide clean date ranges (Task 5.2). Updating old content and uploading new content proceeded via the aggregation pipeline (Tasks 5.3 and 5.4) and the scope of the infrastructure was extended in Task 5.5. From M18, we began to extend the infrastructure to accommodate new ARIADNE subject types, demonstrating the powerful benefits for researchers in being able to cross-search multiple datasets, of different data types, from different data providers. Since M36, we have doubled the number of resources in the public portal. We have also extended work on item level integration, continuing the development of Application Profiles for specific sub-domains, and encouraging usage of the ARIADNEplus Lab VRE, which gives researchers access to a suite of tools which allow them to directly interrogate the ARIADNEplus Knowledge Base. Finally, in Task 5.7, we have collaborated with other catalogues, including the ROAD and THANADOS aggregators, to integrate their data within the ARIADNE Knowledge base. Overall, and in terms of our initial objectives, ARIADNEplus has extended the geographical, temporal, and subject-based coverage of ARIADNE in several dimensions.

8.1 Geographical coverage

Whilst ARIADNE had selective geographic coverage, focussed on Northern and Western Europe, in ARIADNEplus we have provided more comprehensive coverage of the whole of Europe, with a particular focus on southern and eastern Europe, embracing Spain, Portugal, Cyprus, Romania and Serbia (Figure 9). Most notably, we have extended coverage to international partners, including:

- records of digital fieldwork archives covering Pueblo remains in the American South-West from the Centre for Digital Antiquity at Arizona State University,
- records for archaeological sites from the Cordoba region in Argentina and for artefacts from Patagonia, provided by the Argentinian research council, CONICET,
- links to over 139,000 fieldwork reports from Japan provided by the Nara Research Institute for Cultural Properties.

Figure 9: The geographical coverage of ARIADNEplus

8.2 Temporal coverage

The original ARIADNE project was focused on traditional archaeological time periods, but a specific objective of ARIADNEplus was to extend the beginning and the end of the temporal range of resources in the ARIADNE Knowledge Base. Our coverage of early prehistory was achieved by working with our partner CENIEH, which is an international research centre based in Burgos in Spain. Its research activities are mainly on human evolution during the Late Neogene and Quaternary, and include collaborative projects at excavations and deposits of these periods worldwide. In addition, CENIEH is responsible for the conservation, restoration, management and the recording of archaeological and paleontological collections, in particular from Atapuerca. In addition, by welcoming a new Associate partner, ROCEEH, we were able to extend our coverage to early hominid fossils and tools. ROCEEH investigates the phenomenon of early hominin migration and by aggregating their ROAD database within ARIADNE we were able to add coverage of early African and Asian sites. As of 4 December 2022, the portal provided access to 59,385 resources dated to 1,000,000 to -280,000 years BCE.

At the opposite end of the temporal scale, we have extended coverage to embrace recent and contemporary archaeology (Figure 10). There has been a recent upsurge of interest in the archaeology of the Cold War, and our Romanian partner IAVP, provided resources for Communist Farms in the Dobruja region, as well as Ottoman mosques in the region. Other recent resources were provided by UoY-ADS, with the WWII and Cold War Defence of Britain database, as well as resources from Inrap. Metal detector finds made by members of the public in Denmark, Finland and England also made up a high proportion of recent resources. As of 4 December 2022, the portal provided access to 86,232 resources dated AD 1940 to the present day.

Browse when

Scroll on the timeline to zoom. Drag to pan. Hold shift and drag a selection to apply a time range. Click "Display as search result" to search the time range in the catalogue.

Figure 10: The temporal coverage of ARIADNEplus

8.3 Subject-based coverage

Finally, a major objective of ARIADNEplus was to extend the range of sub-domains covered by the infrastructure. Archaeology is a very inter-disciplinary domain, drawing on a range of specialisms, which were brought by many partners (Figure 11). Our initial objectives highlighted a number of new fields and particular highlights include:

- buildings survey, contributed by LNEC and UoY-ADS, with 1,274 resources, as of 4 Dec 2022;
- maritime archaeology, with 33,666 resources, as of 4 Dec 2022;
- archaeological dating evidence, with 9015 resources, as of 4 Dec 2022;
- scientific analyses, drawn from CENIEH, INFN, UoY-ADS, and Umea University, with 7785 resources, as of 4 Dec 2022;
- inscriptions, provided by the University of Barcelona and the Cyprus Institute, with over 83,357 resources, as of 4 Dec 2022.

These resources represent some areas which were previously under-represented and they are important for bringing new audiences and user groups to ARIADNE.

Browse what

Click on a word in the word cloud to make a search in the catalogue.

Figure 11: Word cloud representing some of the subject coverage of ARIADNEplus

In conclusion, work undertaken in WP5 has ensured a significant extension to the ARIADNEplus data infrastructure. The work of the aggregation task has continued during the final months of the current project, ensuring full coverage of all ARIADNEplus partners, as well as the growing number of Associate Partners who wish to use our services to make their data available beyond their national borders. Over the last twelve months it has become clear that many more organisations wish to join ARIADNE and that the consortium must ensure that a resource which has become a key component of the European Research Infrastructure landscape continues to grow, via a sustainable business plan for future activity.

8. References

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